

Association of Biochemical Parameters at Distinct Time Intervals in Hemodialysis Patients

PROJECT REPORT SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE IN MASTER OF CLINICAL LABORATORY SCIENCES IN CLINICAL BIOCHEMISTRY

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the research reported in this thesis represents my own work at King Khalid University. This work has not been previously submitted to the university or any other institution in the application for admission to a degree or other qualification. The thesis was written by myself with guidance from my supervisors.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
SCOT	Saudi Center for Organ Transplantation
KRT	Kidney Replacement Therapy
MOH	Ministry of Health
HD	Hemodialysis
PD	Peritoneal Dialysis
ESRD	End-stage renal Disease
LDL	Low-density lipoprotein
HDL	High-density lipoprotein
TC	Total Cholesterol
CKD	Chronic kidney Disease
BMI	Body Mass Index
KDOQI	Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative
AKI	Acute Kidney Injury
DIH	Dialysis-Induced Hypotension

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The process of hemodialysis (HD) involves the diffusion of molecules along an electrochemical concentration gradient over a portable semi-permeable membrane layer. The main objective of hemodialysis is to regain the fluid focus within and outside the cells, which is a feature of normal kidney function. The reabsorption of nutrients such as glucose, water, amino acids, and certain electrolytes including sodium, chloride, magnesium, potassium, and phosphate occurs in the kidney. The objective of this study is to analyze biochemical parameters in hemodialysis patients.

Method: The study applied correlation analysis to determine the nature of the relationships between the biochemical parameters during hemodialysis. Descriptive statistics were also used to determine the mean concentrations for the parameters during hemodialysis.

Results: The concentrations of urea dropped from 45.12mmol/l from week one to 5.74mmol/l in week four. while the concentration of creatinine dropped from 761.53umol/l from week one to 160.60umol/l in week four. A statistically strong positive and significant correlation between urea and creatinine was found in the study using correlation analysis. Sodium, potassium, calcium, hemoglobin, iron, total iron binding capacity (TIBC), albumin, and phosphorus had their concentrations vary during dialysis weeks, with their concentrations increasing during some weeks and decreasing during others. It was also established that there was a significant negative association between urea and TIBC.

Conclusion: The study established that urea and creatinine concentrations reduced significantly during the fourth week of dialysis compared to the first week of dialysis. Therefore, dialysis helps to remove toxic waste products from the bloodstream.

CHAPTER 1:

INTRODUCTION

A. Background

The process of hemodialysis (HD) involves the diffusion of molecules along an electrochemical concentration gradient over a portable semi-permeable membrane layer. The main objective of hemodialysis is to regain the fluid focus within and outside the cells, which is a feature of normal kidney function (1). HD is a medical machine that helps renal patients remove toxins and excess fluids by filtering the blood when the kidney cannot function or when the rate of glomerular filtration is less than 15%. The dialysis functions are to eliminate salt, extra water, and waste product to avoid accumulating in the body and maintain a level of electrolytes in the bloodstream like sodium, potassium, and bicarbonate. Dialysis keeps blood pressure in the normal range. Dialysis is classified into three types: intermittent hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, and renal replacement therapies (2).

The kidney is one of the essential organs which is bean-shaped with a brown-reddish color and a size of around 12 cm. The kidney's primary function is to manage the fluid volume of the body and eliminate waste products and toxic substances to balance blood pressure (3). The most important chemicals that are removed from the body by the kidneys include urea, creatinine, and uric acid. Urea is a catabolic protein product, and uric acid is produced from the breakdown of nucleic acid. The kidney also clears away the drug residues to prevent that accumulation in the body (4). In the human body, the normal range of pH is 7.35- 7.45 (4).

One of the kidney's chief functions is to secrete the hormone erythropoietin, responsible for producing the RBCs in the bone marrow (5). Kidney promotes vitamin D converted into an active form called calcitriol, which plays an important role in maintaining a balance of calcium, phosphate levels and helping the bones' growth preservation. The renal arteries allow blood to enter the kidney. These arteries split into smaller capillaries, which join the nephrons, a microscopic organ-like structure found inside the kidney. The waste is eliminated by the kidney's nephrons, which also allow essential nutrients to be reabsorbed into the circulation before the filtered blood escapes through the renal veins. The renal cortex surrounds outer the renal medulla (inside), and the renal pelvis (center of the kidney) are the main parts of each kidney. The renal medulla is the kidney's inner part; the medulla's primary function is to maintain the concentration of urine

Nephrons are the kidney components where the waste is removed, and the vital substances are reabsorbed back to the bloodstream after which the filtered blood leaves through the renal veins. Each kidney consists of an outer renal cortex, an inner renal medulla, and a renal pelvis. The renal medulla is the kidney's inner part; the medulla's primary function is to maintain the concentration of urine (6).

The kidney consists of a million to a million and a half of the nephron's basic unit. The human kidney contains an outer cortical layer that is made up of 85% nephrons. The cortex's importance in the first step is removing waste products, reabsorption of nutrients, and urine concentration. The kidneys' capacity to draw unnecessary blood controls the essential body components, water, and electrolyte substances. In normal kidney function, the processing of renal blood flow is the amount of blood sent to the kidneys per unit of time (7). In the human body, blood is supplied from the renal artery to the kidney. The normal human renal gets roughly 25% of the blood pumped to the heart at all times: there is around 1200 ml/min of total renal blood flow (8). About 40% of patients suffering from high blood pressure and diabetes affect kidney function is evaluated by a few biochemical tests e.g blood serum urea, nitrogen, creatinine, and uric acid level.

Chronic renal disease affects more than 10 percent of people globally, and millions of people die from it. Around 11000 people are suffering from kidney disease in Saudi Arabia, as reported by statistic evaluations in 2014. This means there are more than 600000 people affected by renal failure worldwide (9). Chronic renal failure arises from fat metabolism abnormalities, which present sequences in nephrotic syndrome or renal deficiency. The two main risk factors for end-stage renal disease are diabetes and high blood pressure (8).

Renal failure, also known as end-stage renal disease, is a medical issue where the kidney functions at less than 20% of the average level. Kidney disease is classified into two types: acute renal failure and chronic renal failure. The onset of acute renal failure is fast and can be treated, but chronic renal failure develops slowly and can be treated only by organ transplantation (10). Symptoms and signs may include vomiting, leg swelling, food aversion, embarrassment, and sleep disturbance. Problems of acute failure include hyperkalemia, hypertrophy, and a high level of urea in the blood. Acute renal failure causes hypotension, urinary tract infection, some drugs, and hemolytic uremic illness (8).

The acute renal disease commonly occurs when the blood flow to the kidney is stopped suddenly, disrupted or when the renal functions are overwhelmed with toxins and drugs. Drug and chemical overdose of antibiotics or chemotherapy may result in acute renal disease. Patients suffering from acute failure need supportive treatment to avoid the disease's complications (11).

The primary treatment line for patients with sudden loss of renal function or who have reached end-stage renal disease is hemodialysis. Excess toxic fluids and metabolic waste products are eliminated from the body during this process (12). Hemodialysis is a process that uses a machine to filter wastes, salts, and liquids from the blood when the kidneys are no longer capable of carrying out their function. Despite failing kidneys, the procedure can help maintain an active lifestyle with hemodilution management experience (13). Hemodialysis involves replacing the kidney function artificially, especially in situations of renal failure. Dialysis cannot fully restore lost kidney function. However, by diffusion and ultrafiltration, it can partially control renal functions.

Urea is the key concentration of non-protein nitrogen; Urea is manufactured in the liver from CO₂ as well as ammonia. The typical variety of urea in the blood is 5-20 mg/dl. The reduction in urea in the blood is caused because of insufficient protein intake. Elevated urea concentration in the blood is called uremia or azotemia. Uremia is classified right into prerenal, renal, and postrenal. Many causes of uremia are due to a high level of protein diet (14). Creatinine is synthesized as a waste product of creatine metabolism. Creatinine found in the bloodstream is directly proportional to muscle mass. Uric acid results as a final product of purine metabolism in the liver. Normal range of uric acid in the blood serum in males 4.0-8.5 mg/dl in females 2.7-7.3 mg/dl.

Toxic nitrogenous waste deposition can result in symptoms ranging from nausea and vomiting and seizures. Higher blood acidity or metabolic acidosis is caused by decreased excretion of hydrogen ions. Hyperkalemia or potassium overload as a result of decreased potassium excretion can result in ventricular arrhythmias. Typically, hyperkalemia doesn't develop until an advanced stage. Hyperphosphatemia is caused by reduced phosphate excretion, which is caused by high potassium consumption or the use of medications that impede potassium excretion. Low blood calcium levels, also known as hypocalcemia, are a result of the decreased renal synthesis of calcitriol, an active form of vitamin D. The parathyroid gland increases PTH synthesis in response to low blood calcium levels. To raise blood calcium levels, PTH encourages the release of calcium from bones. This process eventually results in an excessive parathyroid gland which can appear before hypocalcemia occurs. Renal osteodystrophy occurs when the bones grow thin and fragile as a result of the constant loss of calcium in the blood (15).

B. Dialysis

The world dialysis increasing international prices of chronic conditions hint a consequent increase in end-stage renal disease which is the last stage of chronic kidney Disease (CKD). This indicates kidneys are only working at 10 to 15 percent of their typical capability. It is the last, irreversible stage of persistent kidney illness, where kidney feature has decreased to the point that the kidneys can no longer work independently. A patient with end-stage kidney failure needs to obtain a dialysis or kidney transplant to endure for more than a few weeks. patients may experience a variety of signs and symptoms as kidney failure advances. These consist of tiredness, sleepiness, reduction in peeing or failure to pee, dehydrated skin, itchy skin, migraine, weight reduction, nausea or vomiting, bone discomfort, skin as well as nail adjustments, and simple bruising. A dialysis electrode tool consists of a shank of a needle created from a hollow dialysis fiber membrane. The Shank is shut at its distal end by a securing plug and, at its proximal end, connected to a supporting chamber specified by a tubular body part. The electrolyte is supplied to the chamber in the Shank via an inlet avenue and is removed through an outlet avenue linked to the supporting chamber. Likewise, the device In carrying out a microanalysis procedure in human cells, the device is topped with an enzyme electrolyte service. Also, electric measurements are taken to concentrate a chemical compound diffusing into the shank chamber through the dialysis fiber Shank (16).

Approximately more than 150 million people suffer from renal failure due to chronic renal disease with a fatality rate of 2.4 million deaths per year (17). In comparison, acute renal failure is the most factor leading to the chronic renal disease that affects about 12 million people globally.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Renal Dialysis in KSA

According to the statistics of dialysis prepared at the end by the Saudi Center for Organ Transplantation (SCOT), there are approximately 271 dialysis centers in Saudi Arabia, having more than 7800 machines caring for around 18000 patients. Among 18000 patients with dialysis, there are around 15% of the patients in the waiting list for kidney transplantation. Out of these patients, about 65% of hemodialysis patients have hypertensive, and the other 50% have diabetes (19).

B. Dialysis Facility in KSA

To assist future preparation of dialysis services in the various geographical areas of Saudi Arabia, there are 130 active HD facilities. According to Saudi Arabia's geographical areas, there were 18 (14%) dialysis centers in the north, 25 (19%) in the south, 13 (10%) in the east, 35 (27%) in the west, and 39 (30%) in the center. 1,793 units (93%) of HD equipment are capable of performing dialysis. 3.5 patients are the typical ratio for each HD equipment. 28 (22%) of the focus groups also had peritoneal dialysis in addition to hemodialysis (PD). In the follow-up of post-transplant patients, 56 (43%) centers (19).

C. Pathology of the Kidney Disease

The clinical experience shows that otherwise drug-induced hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia, specifically in ESRD, are typically the result of a severe insult in a persistent metabolic or hormone state. To characterize the incidence and value of hypoglycemia occasions in ESRD individuals (20).

Moreover, cardiovascular diseases are the primary source of morbidity and death in dialysis individuals. Hypertension in people has been identified as one of the significant classic cardiovascular risk factors of the dialysis age. High blood pressure in renal individuals needs to be provided a specific and ongoing focus, and it ought to be appropriately dealt with considering the raised cardiovascular danger to the patient. Research into the devices of uremia cardiomyopathy and cardio redesigning must supply a precious new understanding and bring about extra precisely targeted and much more effective treatments than in the past (2).

Dialysis-induced hypotension (DIH) is a common problem in treatment. It is commonly associated with symptoms such as muscular cramps, stomach and breast pain, nausea, vomiting, dyspnea, light-headedness, weakness, tension and anxiety, vertigo, and paleness as well as perspiration, all of which considerably reduce the patient's quality of life. Dialysis hypotension is also a risk factor for death in the dialyzed population. The link between mortality and DIH in persistent hemodialysis patients has been referred to as paradoxical or reverse epidemiology, in contrast to the public and ubiquitous usual risk factors such as high blood pressure and hypercholesterolemia.

It was shown that significantly more individuals died from hemodialysis when high blood pressure was reduced. Intense intradialytic hypotonia decreases coronary blood flow. Myocardial anemia can lead to cardiac arrest, arrhythmia, and possibly a heart attack. DIH with accompanying hypoperfusion, particularly if prolonged, can harm other essential organs such as the brain and the gastrointestinal system. It may also contribute to chronic overhydration due to an inability to achieve a total dry weight.

It is also a challenge to provide appropriate dialysis dosage, which causes additional morbidity and death (21).

When a persistent disease of kidney is identified, an effort should be made to identify and treat certain underlying conditions. The Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative (KDOQI).

KDOQI guidelines establish important treatment objectives for all patients suffering from chronic kidney disease. These goals include slowing down condition development, finding and treating issues, and managing cardio danger elements. Medical care doctors have an essential duty to find chronic kidney illness early, set up actions to reduce condition progression, and give a timely referral to a nephrologist (22).

A high body mass index (BMI; in kg/m²) relates to rise in heart disease and all-cause mortality in the primary population. Nonetheless, the impact of overweight (BMI: 25- 30) in patients with a chronic kidney condition (CKD) going through upkeep hemodialysis is occurs in the opposite direction; a high BMI relates to enhanced lifespan. Although this "reverse epidemiology" of weight gain or dialysis-risk-paradox is relatively constant in HD individuals, studies patients with chronic kidney conditions treated with peritoneal Dialysis have given combined outcomes (23).

Conventional threat aspects, consisting of plasma lipids, in cardio illness pathogenesis in persistent dialysis individuals are uncertain. Previous researches have recommended that reduced product amount to cholesterol (TC) is connected with more significant mortality in people on persistent hemodialysis (HD). Whether this relationship specifies to the HD population or is common to the uremic state is vague. Today's study reviewed the organization of triglycerides with medical results in chronic peritoneal dialysis (PD) people (23).

Glomerular filtering rate is vice versa connected with heart disease independent of formal threat aspects. A raised danger of heart disease is also present at small degrees of kidney problems. Patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) who require dialysis are most at risk. Kidney disease alters the amount, composition, and quality of blood lipids, favoring an atherogenic account. Patients with sophisticated chronic renal disease or (ESRD) show a distinct lipid pattern of hypertriglyceridemia and lower HDL-cholesterol levels while maintaining normal LDL-cholesterol levels. In the general population, there is a definite link between LDL cholesterol, coronary heart disease, and ischemic stroke. Nevertheless, in individuals with ESRD, LDL-cholesterol shows an adverse organization at second-rate LDL-cholesterol degrees and a weakly favorable organization with death at increased LDL-cholesterol degrees. According to available data, decreasing LDL cholesterol helps avoid severe atherosclerotic events in patients with chronic renal disease and kidney transplant recipients but is ineffective in patients requiring dialysis.

Lipid abnormalities may influence the clinical results of dialysis patients. According to recent research findings, HDL insufficiency is a marker of ESRD. This study compared HDL composition and HDL performance parameters in hemodialysis (HD) and peritoneal dialysis (PD) patients to healthy and balanced controls. A compositional study indicated that HDL through both dialysis groups shifted toward a more proinflammatory phenotype, with significant changes in the lipid moiety and protein composition. In HD patients, function, cholesterol efflux, and anti-inflammatory and antiapoptotic characteristics appeared to be significantly reduced. The HDL-associated paraoxon task, on the other hand, was most affordable in persons with PD (24).

D. Aim of the study

To find the association between the results of the biochemistry laboratory using blood samples that were sent by the hemodialysis department among 130 dialysis patients. Also, checking the extent of the effect of hemodialysis on the results of the examination during the first week to the fourth week of starting dialysis.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

A. Sample

Around 130 patients with chronic kidney failure were given hemodialysis in King Khalid Hospital Tabuk, collecting patient data from the first week until the fourth week was selected for this study. The age of patients on hemodialysis in the age group of 17 to 81 years consisted of males and females. The patients undergoing renal Dialysis were tested for serum urea, serum creatinine, sodium, potassium, calcium, hemoglobin, Iron, TIBC albumin, and phosphorus in Table 1. Patient inclusion and exclusion Table 2.

Patients group hemodialysis

Number of patients	130 patients	
Gender	Male 67(52%) / female 63(48%)	
Age (years)	17-81	
Patients above 60 years old	10 patients	
Hemodialysis per-week	All patients doing dialysis three-time pre-week	
Diabetes mellites	65	
Hypertension	61	
Heart disease	55	
Obesity	27	
Family history	72	

Table 1: Patients' Group – Hemodialysis

B. Sampling Procedure

The procedure of collecting a sample of patients until receiving the results. First, identify the patient's name and id. Second, prepare the equipment for collecting patients' samples (gloves, alcohol pads, protective tip, 5 ml syringe, vacutainer adopter for syringe, normal saline, and laboratory tubes). A sample of blood is drawn from the patient during hemodialysis by inserting a needle into a vein. They put the blood into tubes to be sent to the laboratory to examine the analyses and send the reports. The required analyzes are about kidney function. Each patient has a unique file number to follow up on the results of the patients. Patient analyzes are done every week.

Patients' inclusion	Patients' exclusion
<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Adult male and female patients (greater than 17 years old) with chronic kidney disease- Dialysis indications of acute renal failure- Patient with diabetes mellites that needs medication- Hypertension- Obesity	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Prior treatment of plasma cell myeloma with chemotherapy- Clinical diagnosis of liver dysfunction- Pregnant women- Recognized advanced chronic renal failure- Confirmation of damage on the renal biopsy- Renal replacement therapy- Dialysis patient's kidney transplant

Table 2: Patient's Inclusion and Exclusion Criterion

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

For patients undergoing dialysis, the biochemical parameters were analyzed (Table -3). A significant drop in urea (Figure-1) and creatinine (Figure-2) levels was observed throughout the study period.

Biochemical Report post-four-week dialysis											
Time		Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (umol/l)	Sodium (mmol/l)	Potassium (mmol/l)	Calcium (mmol/l)	HGB (g/dl)	Iron (umol/l)	TIBC (mmol/l)	Albumin (g/l)	phosphorus (mmol/l)
First Week	Mean	45.12	761.53	138.37	4.32	8.57	11.54	20.54	34.17	35.62	4.65
	Std. Deviation	22.236	323.207	3.392	.749	1.126	1.735	9.008	8.482	5.202	.815
Second Week	Mean	20.99	532.05	135.92	4.02	8.28	11.68	14.35	39.58	37.38	5.00
	Std. Deviation	8.688	134.939	183.175	66.804	1.066	9.126	4.838	8.605	3.936	4.052
Third Week	Mean	12.05	395.56	138.17	4.46	5.76	12.28	16.88	42.75	38.18	5.38
	Std. Deviation	5.190	95.829	3.892	.882	1.351	2.023	8.784	9.620	5.097	3.597
Fourth Week	Mean	5.74	160.60	137.86	4.38	4.25	11.40	13.75	36.39	34.05	4.73
	Std. Deviation	2.457	102.563	4.409	.999	1.079	1.881	5.831	10.337	4.433	.795

Table 3: biochemical report post-four-week dialysis

Table 3 shows the average values of the biochemical parameters from week one to week four of the dialysis period.

Fig. 1: Urea Levels

• Figure-2

Fig. 2: Creatinine Levels

When evaluated for the cross-correlations between the average value biochemical parameters post first week of the renal dialysis (Table-3), a significant cross-correlation between urea vs sodium, Hgb, iron, TIBC, albumin, and phosphorus was observed. A cross-correlation with sodium vs Hgb, iron, and phosphorus was observed. A correlation between Hgb, albumin, and phosphorus was observed. albumin is correlated with phosphorus. Total biochemical cross-correlations were 19.

		Week – 1: Correlations									
		Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (umol/l)	Sodium (mmol/l)	Potassium (mmol/l)	Calcium (mmol/l)	HG (g/dl)	Iron (umol/l)	TIBC (mmol/l)	Albumin (g/l)	phosphorus (mmol/l)
Urea (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	1	.063	.276**	.122	-.057	-.346**	-.623**	.230**	.189*	.306**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.480	.001	.167	.525	.000	.000	.010	.031	.000
Creatinine (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.063	1	-.153	.038	-.010	-.029	.031	.002	-.004	.058
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.480		.083	.670	.911	.742	.723	.983	.965	.513
Sodium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.276**	-.153	1	.011	-.065	-.207*	-.276**	.112	.062	.230**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.083		.904	.468	.018	.001	.212	.480	.009

Potassium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.122	.038	.011	1	.166	-.135	.003	-.137	.057	.176*
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.167	.670	.904		.061	.126	.975	.126	.517	.045
Calcium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.057	-.010	-.065	.166	1	.096	.065	-.081	.021	.169
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.525	.911	.468	.061		.283	.467	.371	.818	.056
HG(g/dl)	Pearson Correlation	- .346**	-.029	-.207*	-.135	.096	1	.431**	-.135	-.056	-.149
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.742	.018	.126	.283		.000	.131	.531	.090
Iron (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	- .623**	.031	-.276**	.003	.065	.431**	1	-.038	-.223*	-.307**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.723	.001	.975	.467	.000		.671	.011	.000
TIBC (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.230**	.002	.112	-.137	-.081	-.135	-.038	1	-.126	-.025
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.010	.983	.212	.126	.371	.131	.671		.161	.784
Albumin (g/l)	Pearson Correlation	.189*	-.004	.062	.057	.021	-.056	-.223*	-.126	1	.190*
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.031	.965	.480	.517	.818	.531	.011	.161		.031
phosphorus (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.306**	.058	.230**	.176*	.169	-.149	-.307**	-.025	.190*	1
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.513	.009	.045	.056	.090	.000	.784	.031	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4: Week – 1: Correlations

Table 4 shows the cross-correlations between the biochemical parameters for the first-week dialysis.

After the second week of dialysis, the cross-correlations between the average value biochemical parameters were evaluated (table-5). A significant cross correlation between urea vs sodium and potassium was observed. Correlation between creatinine and sodium and potassium was observed. Sodium values also correlated with potassium and TIBC. A correlation between potassium and TIBC was evident. phosphorus correlated with calcium. A correlation between Albumin with Iron was also observed. Total biochemical cross-correlations were 9.

Week – 2: Correlations											
		Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (umol/l)	Sodium (mmol/l)	Potassium (mmol/l)	Calcium (mmol/l)	HGB (g/dl)	Iron (umol/l)	TIBC (mmol/l)	Albumin (g/l)	phosphorus (mmol/l)
Urea (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	1	.135	.308*	.372**	.079	-.084	-.039	-.152	.039	-.020
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.125	.000	.000	.373	.340	.659	.084	.662	.819
Creatinine (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.135	1	.317*	.344**	.163	-.068	.000	-.038	-.032	.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.125		.000	.000	.064	.445	.999	.671	.721	.568
Sodium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.308*	.317*	1	.898**	.103	-.080	-.058	-.485**	-.035	.054
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.245	.363	.510	.000	.693	.539
Potassium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.372*	.344*	.898*	1	.088	-.094	-.124	-.538**	-.046	.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.318	.286	.161	.000	.602	.554
Calcium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.079	.163	.103	.088	1	-.019	.050	-.099	.081	.172*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.373	.064	.245	.318		.827	.573	.264	.360	.050
HGB (g/dl)	Pearson Correlation	-.084	-.068	-.080	-.094	-.019	1	.146	.054	.110	.009
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.340	.445	.363	.286	.827		.097	.540	.212	.923
Iron (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.039	.000	-.058	-.124	.050	.146	1	.119	.212*	.038
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.659	.999	.510	.161	.573	.097		.176	.015	.668
TIBC (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.152	-.038	-.485*	-.538**	-.099	.054	.119	1	.147	.013
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.084	.671	.000	.000	.264	.540	.176		.095	.882
Albumin (g/l)	Pearson Correlation	.039	-.032	-.035	-.046	.081	.110	.212*	.147	1	.096
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.662	.721	.693	.602	.360	.212	.015	.095		.276
phosphorus (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.020	.050	.054	.052	.172*	.009	.038	.013	.096	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.819	.568	.539	.554	.050	.923	.668	.882	.276	
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).											
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).											

Table 5: Week -2: Correlations

Table 5 shows the cross-correlations between the biochemical parameters for the second-week dialysis.

When evaluated for the cross-correlations between the average value biochemical parameters after the third week of the renal dialysis (Table-6), albumin correlated with sodium. calcium correlated with Hgb. A correlation between TIBC and Hgb was evident. Correlation with TIBC vs iron was observed. Total biochemical cross-correlations were 4.

Week – 3: Correlations											
		Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (umol/l)	Sodium (mmol/l)	Potassium (mmol/l)	Calcium (mmol/l)	HGB (g/dl)	Iron (umol/l)	TIBC (mmol/l)	Albumin (g/l)	phosphorus (mmol/l)
Urea (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	1	.022	-.059	.050	-.094	-.154	.020	-.034	-.029	.028
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.801	.506	.569	.286	.081	.826	.703	.745	.752
Creatinine (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.022	1	.062	.153	-.040	-.018	-.101	-.072	.029	-.001
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.801		.481	.081	.650	.838	.252	.417	.747	.989
Sodium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.059	.062	1	-.113	-.085	.006	.019	.018	-.192*	-.094
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.506	.481		.199	.336	.948	.833	.843	.029	.285
Potassium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.050	.153	-.113	1	.106	.067	-.125	-.136	-.134	-.027
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.569	.081	.199		.230	.450	.156	.123	.129	.760
Calcium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.094	-.040	-.085	.106	1	.180*	-.026	-.064	-.013	.014
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.286	.650	.336	.230		.040	.770	.467	.884	.872
HGB (g/dl)	Pearson Correlation	-.154	-.018	.006	.067	.180*	1	.124	.249**	-.048	-.053
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.081	.838	.948	.450	.040		.162	.004	.590	.548
Iron (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.020	-.101	.019	-.125	-.026	.124	1	.234**	.060	-.065
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.826	.252	.833	.156	.770	.162		.007	.501	.460
TIBC (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.034	-.072	.018	-.136	-.064	.249**	.234**	1	.131	.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.703	.417	.843	.123	.467	.004	.007		.136	.556
Albumin (g/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.029	.029	-.192*	-.134	-.013	-.048	.060	.131	1	.102
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.745	.747	.029	.129	.884	.590	.501	.136		.250
phosphorus (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.028	-.001	-.094	-.027	.014	-.053	-.065	.052	.102	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.752	.989	.285	.760	.872	.548	.460	.556	.250	
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).											
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).											

Table 6: Week – 3: Correlations

Table 6 shows the cross-correlations between the biochemical parameters for the third-week dialysis.

After the fourth week of dialysis, the cross-correlations between the average value and biochemical parameters were evaluated (Table 7). A correlation between phosphorus and creatinine, sodium Vs potassium, and phosphorus vs TIBC was observed. Total biochemical cross-correlations were 3.

		Week – 4: Correlations									
		Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (umol/l)	Sodium (mmol/l)	Potassium (mmol/l)	Calcium (mmol/l)	HGB (g/dl)	Iron (umol/l)	TIBC (mmol/l)	Albumin (g/l)	phosphorus (mmol/l)
Urea (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	1	-.152	.004	.114	-.126	.038	-.019	-.009	-.045	-.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.085	.967	.200	.156	.669	.831	.916	.612	.409
Creatinine (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.152	1	-.088	.009	.067	.017	-.031	.079	.087	.221*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.085		.321	.922	.450	.849	.722	.369	.327	.012
Sodium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.004	-.088	1	.202*	-.100	-.095	.025	.077	-.023	.040
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.967	.321		.021	.256	.282	.779	.385	.795	.650
Potassium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.114	.009	.202*	1	.012	-.142	-.070	.012	.020	.044
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.200	.922	.021		.891	.108	.428	.890	.823	.623
Calcium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.126	.067	-.100	.012	1	.136	.080	.166	-.022	.087
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.156	.450	.256	.891		.125	.366	.058	.802	.326
HGB (g/dl)	Pearson Correlation	.038	.017	-.095	-.142	.136	1	.173	.105	.100	.051
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.669	.849	.282	.108	.125		.050	.235	.261	.564
Iron (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.019	-.031	.025	-.070	.080	.173	1	.144	.086	-.018
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.831	.722	.779	.428	.366	.050		.102	.331	.841
TIBC (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.009	.079	.077	.012	.166	.105	.144	1	.131	.276**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.916	.369	.385	.890	.058	.235	.102		.136	.001
Albumin (g/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.045	.087	-.023	.020	-.022	.100	.086	.131	1	.017
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.612	.327	.795	.823	.802	.261	.331	.136		.845
phosphorus (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.073	.221*	.040	.044	.087	.051	-.018	.276**	.017	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.409	.012	.650	.623	.326	.564	.841	.001	.845	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7: Week – 4: Correlations

Table 7 shows the cross-correlations between the biochemical parameters after the fourth-week dialysis.

With the average of all parameters in four-week dialysis, the correlation between urea Vs creatinine and TIBC vs phosphorus was observed (Table-8). Total biochemical cross-correlations were 2.

Complete Average four-week Correlations

		Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (umol/l)	Sodium (mmol/l)	Potassium (mmol/l)	Calcium (mmol/l)	HGB (g/dl)	Iron (umol/l)	TIBC (mmol/l)	Albumin (g/l)	phosphorus (mmol/l)
Urea (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	1	.953*	.003	-.581	.847	-.223	.850	-.568	.011	-.453
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.047	.997	.419	.153	.777	.150	.432	.989	.547
Creatinine (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.953*	1	.187	-.532	.941	.009	.800	-.307	.305	-.196
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.047		.813	.468	.059	.991	.200	.693	.695	.804
Sodium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.003	.187	1	-.604	.506	-.077	-.436	.241	.388	.122
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.997	.813		.396	.494	.923	.564	.759	.612	.878
Potassium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.581	-.532	-.604	1	-.700	.708	-.071	.615	.264	.673
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.419	.468	.396		.300	.292	.929	.385	.736	.327
Calcium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.847	.941	.506	-.700	1	-.059	.550	-.223	.364	-.169
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.153	.059	.494	.300		.941	.450	.777	.636	.831
HGB (g/dl)	Pearson Correlation	-.223	.009	-.077	.708	-.059	1	.127	.872	.863	.950
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.777	.991	.923	.292	.941		.873	.128	.137	.050
Iron (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.850	.800	-.436	-.071	.550	.127	1	-.361	.107	-.182
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.150	.200	.564	.929	.450	.873		.639	.893	.818
TIBC (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.568	-.307	.241	.615	-.223	.872	-.361	1	.812	.981*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.432	.693	.759	.385	.777	.128	.639		.188	.019
Albumin (g/l)	Pearson Correlation	.011	.305	.388	.264	.364	.863	.107	.812	1	.856
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.989	.695	.612	.736	.636	.137	.893	.188		.144
phosphorus (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.453	-.196	.122	.673	-.169	.950	-.182	.981*	.856	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.547	.804	.878	.327	.831	.050	.818	.019	.144	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 8: Complete Average four-week Correlations

Table 8 shows the cross-correlations between the biochemical parameters for all the fourth weeks of dialysis. Analysis revealed that the concentrations of urea creatinine dropped in week four to compared week one of the hemodialysis; the mean concentrations of urea and creatinine were lower in the post-dialysis compared to pre-dialysis.

Complete all four-week Separate Correlations											
		Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (umol/l)	Sodium (mmol/l)	Potassium (mmol/l)	Calcium (mmol/l)	HGB (g/dl)	Iron (umol/l)	TIBC (mmol/l)	Albumin (g/l)	phosphorus (mmol/l)
Urea (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	1	.518**	.058	.064	.541**	-.068	.018	-.104*	.060	-.012
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.186	.148	.000	.120	.686	.018	.170	.784
Creatinine (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.518**	1	.164**	.173**	.538**	-.026	.167**	-.080	.072	.008
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.558	.000	.069	.100	.855
Sodium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.058	.164**	1	.935**	.276**	-.064	-.106*	-.122**	.063	.039
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.186	.000		.000	.000	.144	.015	.006	.151	.379
Potassium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.064	.173**	.935**	1	.292**	-.071	-.127**	-.131**	.067	.037
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.148	.000	.000		.000	.105	.004	.003	.129	.395
Calcium (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.541**	.538**	.276**	.292**	1	.015	.170**	-.069	.110*	.030
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.727	.000	.117	.012	.501
HGB (g/dl)	Pearson Correlation	-.068	-.026	-.064	-.071	.015	1	.117**	.068	.059	.003
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.120	.558	.144	.105	.727		.008	.122	.181	.944
Iron (umol/l)	Pearson Correlation	.018	.167**	-.106*	-.127**	.170**	.117**	1	.058	.002	-.049
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.686	.000	.015	.004	.000	.008		.187	.961	.268
TIBC (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.104*	-.080	-.122**	-.131**	-.069	.068	.058	1	.151**	.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.018	.069	.006	.003	.117	.122	.187		.001	.098
Albumin (g/l)	Pearson Correlation	.060	.072	.063	.067	.110*	.059	.002	.151**	1	.106*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.170	.100	.151	.129	.012	.181	.961	.001		.016
phosphorus (mmol/l)	Pearson Correlation	-.012	.008	.039	.037	.030	.003	-.049	.073	.106*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.784	.855	.379	.395	.501	.944	.268	.098	.016	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Family history

Table 9: Complete all four-week separate correlations

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

A. Discussion

To find the relationship between the results of the biochemistry laboratory using blood samples that were sent by the hemodialysis department among 130 dialysis patients. Also, checking the extent of the effect of hemodialysis on the results of the examination during the first week to the fourth week of starting dialysis. In the analysis, it was established that there was a significant drop in the concentrations of urea and creatinine. Concentrations of urea dropped from 45.12 mmol/l (± 22.24) in week one to 5.74 mmol/l (± 2.46) in week four, while the concentration of creatinine dropped from 761.53 mmol/l (± 323.21) in week one to 160.60 mmol/l (± 102.56) in week four, this is consistent with (25) who established that the mean concentrations of urea and creatinine were decreased after dialysis compared before dialysis, they established that toxic wastes like urea and creatinine are removed in by dialysis. The four-week average revealed that there was a statistically significant positive correlation between urea and creatinine, $r = 0.953$, $p < 0.05$, this is consistent with (26). Who determined that there is a statistically significant positive correlation between Urea and creatinine in patients with chronic renal diseases.

The sodium, potassium, calcium, Hgb, iron, TIBC, albumin, and phosphorus had their concentrations vary during the weeks of dialysis, with their concentrations increasing during some weeks and decreasing during others. This is consistent with the reported literature (13). There is no statistically significant difference in sodium, potassium, calcium, and iron pre and post-dialysis. During the first week of dialysis, urea and creatinine had a significant positive correlation with sodium and potassium; during the next two to four weeks of dialysis, there is no significant correlation between urea and creatinine and both sodium and potassium. The analysis also established that when correlations were carried out separately for the four weeks, there was a significant negative correlation between urea and TIBC, this is consistent with (27). There tend to be low concentrations of Iron. The analysis also determined that for the average four-week correlation, TIBC had a strong positive correlation with phosphorus.

B. Conclusion

One of the kidney's physiologic functions entails removing waste products and fluids from the bloodstream and disposing of them via the urine route. If this function fails in a human being, then one of the treatments applied is hemodialysis, in which the removal of excess toxic body fluids and metabolic end products from the body. Hemodialysis uses machines to filter wastes, salts, and fluid from the human blood. This study involved the correlation analysis of the biochemical parameters in patients undergoing hemodialysis. The study established that there was a significant decrease in the concentration of urea and creatinine during the fourth week of dialysis compared to the first week of dialysis, this can be attributed to the fact that dialysis plays an important role in the removal of toxic wastes like urea and creatinine. The analysis also revealed that there was a significant strong positive correlation between the concentrations of urea and creatinine in patients with kidney infections. The study also determined that there was a significant negative correlation between urea and TIBC. It was also established that the other biochemical parameters like calcium, Hgb, iron, TIBC, sodium, albumin, and phosphorus did not show a consistent change during the weeks of hemodialysis, sometimes their concentrations increased and other times it decreased.

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